

Capacity Building for Open Science: Ukrainian case study

Sofiia Zherebchuk¹, Dmytro Kudas¹

¹*The State Scientific and Technical Library of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine*

Purpose

Ukraine's integration into the European Research Area (ERA) has accelerated the adoption of Open Science principles, positioning transparency, collaboration, and accessibility at the core of its research ecosystem. However, the country faces unique challenges due to the war and post-conflict recovery, limited awareness and resources, and decentralized research systems. This paper examines the pivotal role of the State Scientific and Technical Library of Ukraine (SSTL of Ukraine) in advancing Open Science, particularly through the development of the Ukrainian Research Information System (URIS), implementation of FAIR principals and participation in international projects under Horizon Europe. We explore how SSTL of Ukraine bridges policymakers, researchers, and international organizations to foster an environment aligned with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles and European Open Science policies.

Methods

This study employs a qualitative analysis of Open Science implementation in Ukraine, focusing on policy frameworks, institutional initiatives, and international collaborations. We analyze SSTL's contributions to Open Science through its projects, particularly in research data management, open-access publishing, and the use of persistent identifiers such as ORCID. Additionally, we assess URIS as a Current Research Information System (CRIS), examining its interoperability with European infrastructures like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Data were gathered from policy documents, institutional reports, and participation in Horizon Europe projects.

Discussion

Until 2016, the primary responsibilities of the SSTL of Ukraine revolved around the proper storage and management of information on paper. However, in response to evolving demands, SSTL began implementing significant changes to its objectives, tasks, and tools. In 2017, the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine took steps to grant Ukrainian scientists access to essential electronic scientific resources, designating SSTL as the administrator of this initiative.

That same year, higher education institutions and research organizations in Ukraine gained access to major abstract and bibliographic databases, Scopus and Web of Science, for the first time. Following a selection process, 68 institutions were granted access to Scopus, and 64 to Web of Science. By 2018, the number of institutions with access to these databases had increased to 135 for Scopus and 105 for Web of Science.

Since 2019, access to Scopus and Web of Science has been provided through a national subscription, enabling over 500 higher education and research institutions to utilize these resources over the past three years. Additionally, Ukrainian scientists have gained access to full-text databases from leading global scientific publishers, funded by the state budget. In 2020, access to Springer Nature's electronic books and journals was provided, followed by Elsevier's electronic book collection in 2021.

However, in 2022, due to the war, state budget funding for access to electronic scientific resources became unavailable. Despite this, many publishers and companies have supported Ukraine by offering free access to their electronic resources for Ukrainian scientists, either by maintaining existing subscriptions or opening new ones.

On November 12, 2019, following the successful implementation of access to scientometric databases, Ukraine launched the Open Ukrainian Citation Index (OUCI), a new service for scientists. SSTL introduced the concept of OUCI in spring 2018 (Cheberkus & Nazarovets, 2019). OUCI is a search engine and citation database that aggregates data from publications supporting the Initiative for Open Citations, which is backed by most leading global scientific publishers.

Unlike similar services, OUCI is entirely non-commercial, offering free and open access to all users. The database is populated transparently and includes mechanisms to prevent citation manipulation. OUCI allows users to filter searches to include only publications indexed in Scopus, Web of Science Core Collection, and Ukraine's List of Scientific Journals (categories A and B). This service is designed to provide valuable information and data analysis tools for the scientific community, including researchers, educators, students, journal editors, businesses, grant providers, and academic managers.

The development of OUCI was carried out within the standard funding framework for scientific activities at SSTL, without additional government resources. The result is a scientific and software product that represents Ukraine's step toward integrating into the global scientific community by leveraging open citation data. SSTL has enhanced this initiative by adding analytical tools based on Crossref's open data, making it easier for scientists to access and analyze this information.

The work on OUCI highlighted challenges related to research data management, prompting the initiation of the FAIR project. High-quality metadata is essential for Open Science and adherence to FAIR principles. Without detailed metadata, research data remains invisible and difficult to use. The growing demand for transparency in scientific institutions has increased interest in research data, metadata, and electronic information systems. Another significant project undertaken by SSTL, under the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, was the development of the national Current Research Information System (URIS). CRIS systems are designed to collect, store, disseminate, and analyze research information, making it accessible and usable. Ukraine, in its efforts to integrate into the global scientific community, has adopted best practices in transparent science and innovation policy, leveraging international and national standards such as OpenAIRE, FAIR principles, and CERIF data format.

The lack of accessible and centralized research information in Ukraine has hindered effective decision-making and reporting. URIS aims to address this by automating data collection, improving metadata quality, and creating a unified access point for research information. The system is designed to ensure data reliability, interoperability, and compliance with FAIR principles, enabling better evaluation and decision-making in scientific management.

During the implementation of URIS, SSTL faced challenges, including the need to digitize processes at the Ministry of Education and Science and improve data quality. As a result, URIS expanded to include the digitization of procedures related to research evaluation and funding. The system's functional modules ensure that data is interoperable and complies with FAIR principles from the design stage.

In 2020, Ukraine began developing its national CRIS system, URIS, as mandated by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and the Ministry of Education and Science. URIS was designed to consolidate data on scientific and technical activities in Ukraine, addressing issues of data digitization, quality, and accessibility. The system's functions include aggregating scientific data, automating processes, providing verified data, and offering analytical tools for research.

Key outcomes of URIS include:

- Ensuring transparency of Ukrainian scientific data.
- Simplifying access to information, resources, and services for scientific research.
- Facilitating the search for project collaborators.
- Streamlining the preparation of analytical reports for decision-making.
- Simplifying application and reporting procedures for scientists and institutions

In 2022, SSTL also began collaborating with ORCID to establish the National ORCID Consortium, enabling Ukrainian institutions to integrate ORCID into their systems. Due to the ongoing conflict, ORCID waived membership fees for Ukrainian participants from 2022 to 2025.

Results

1. Strengthening National Open Science Infrastructure

SSTL of Ukraine has emerged as the key institutional driver of Open Science in Ukraine, collaborating with the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine to shape national policies. The Ukrainian Research Information System (URIS) consolidates metadata on research projects, outputs, institutions, and infrastructures, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles (Zharinova, 2024). As a CRIS, URIS enhances transparency and accessibility, facilitating international collaboration through alignment with EOSC.

2. Capacity Building through International Projects

Participation in Horizon Europe-funded initiatives has significantly contributed to Ukraine's Open Science development (Zharinova, 2023). SSTL's involvement in other European projects has provided opportunities to develop national competencies in persistent identifiers, metadata curation, and open-access publishing.

3. Addressing Challenges in Open Science Implementation

Despite progress, Ukraine faces structural barriers, including insufficient awareness of Open Science among researchers, fragmentation of research information, and limited financial resources. SSTL has undertaken targeted training programs, workshops, and policy advisory efforts to address these gaps. By fostering collaborations with European partners, SSTL aims to bridge knowledge and infrastructure disparities, ensuring a resilient and interconnected research environment.

Value

This paper highlights Ukraine's advancements in Open Science, emphasizing the critical role of institutional leadership, strategic international partnerships, and digital research infrastructure. SSTL's initiatives provide a replicable model for post-conflict countries seeking to rebuild their research ecosystems through Open Science. The study underscores the importance of sustained investment in Open Science policies, training, and cross-border collaborations to ensure long-term research excellence and integration into the global scientific community.

References

- ZHARINOVA, A. H., ZHARINOV, S. S., & RYBALKO, Y. V.. (2024). Ways of Development of the National Electronic Scientific Information System as a Tool for Implementing the State Open Science Policy in Ukraine. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, (9), 131–139. https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2024_314985
- ZHARINOVA, A. H., ZHARINOV, S. S., & HAUSCHKE, C. (2023). The New Business Model for the State Scientific and Technical Library of Ukraine Enhancing New Digital Tools for Researchers. *University Library at a New Stage of Social Communications Development. Conference Proceedings*, (8), 202–212. https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2023_293957
- Serhii Zharinov, Danica Zendulková, Iryna Tsybenko, Sophia Zhrebchuk, The importance for Ukrainian R&D system RI's mapping and the Slovak case study, *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 249, 2024, Pages 40-50, ISSN 1877-0509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.048>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050924032599>)
- Cheberkus, D., & Nazarovets, S. (2019). Ukrainian open index maps local citations. *Nature*, 575(7784), 596. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-03662-6> (in English)